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Homeotropic orientation of ion-channel forming mesophase induced by nanotemplate wetting

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Anodic Aluminum Oxide (AAO) membranes were used as templates to control orientation of an ion-channel forming columnar mesophase obtained by self assembly of a wedge-shaped sulfonate molecule. Inside the AAO structure, the director vector of the mesophase is oriented parallel to the pore axis due to confinement effect. The molecular arrangement induced by the spatial confinement within the pores is extended over several microns into the remnant film of the AAO surface. The homeotropic alignment of the channels promotes unidimensional ion conduction through the film plane, which manifests as a considerable increase in conductivity relative to isotropic samples.

Introduction

Generation of supramolecular structures with different dimensionalities (1D-3D) through self-assembly has proven to be a powerful tool for designing materials with tailored properties.^[1-2] The anisotropic physical characteristics of columnar mesophases have attracted considerable interest because of their potential use in various fields.^[3-6] For a number of practical applications, it is desirable to achieve uniaxially oriented and highly ordered columnar superstructures on a macroscopic scale.^[7-9] In-plane alignment is considered as thermodynamically more stable, however, for photovoltaic cells, light-emitting diodes (LEDs),^[10-11] or ion-conducting membranes ^[12-15] metastable homeotropic alignment—with the columnar axis oriented perpendicular to the substrate or membrane plane—is necessary. Several factors affect the orientation of liquid crystals (LC) in open films; among others, the orientation can be correlated with the surface energy of the substrate and the chemical structure of the mesogen.^[16-17] Interfacial

interactions can play a central role in controlling molecular orientation through differences in surface tension between air/LC and LC/substrate interfaces.^[18] Various approaches have been shown to be effective in achieving homeotropic alignment of columnar mesophases in open films, including tuning the surface energy, controlling annealing conditions based on film thickness, or using nanopatterned surfaces.^[15, 19-24] One of the ways to achieve homeotropic alignment can be the use of porous nanotemplates for example based on anodic aluminum oxide (AAO).^[25, 26] The AAO are formed by the electrochemical anodization of aluminum wafers and consists of a parallel array of pores with pore axes well-ordered on a 2D plane, which makes the structure resembling a honeycomb. In addition, the pore diameter can be tailored in a wide range from 8 to 500 nm, depending on the anodization process conditions.^[26] The use of AAO nanotemplates for structuring of functional materials helped improving the proton mobility and subsequently proton conductivity for proton exchange membranes ^[27], allowed to control orientations and ordering of conjugated polymers ^[28] and made it possible to obtain one-dimensional supramolecular wires of discotic molecules with the columnar axes uniformly oriented along pore axes on a macroscopic scale.^[29]

In the present work, we focus on the supramolecular self-assembly of amphiphilic molecules bearing a sulfonate group at its focal point, which were previously shown to create columnar structures with well-defined ion-conducting channels.^[30-31] In particular, the studies have been carried out on a wedge-shaped sulfonate molecule, sodium 2,3,4-tris(11'-acryloylundecyl-1'-oxy)benzene-sulfonate (A-Na). Depending on temperature and relative humidity (RH) conditions, lamellar, columnar, or bicontinuous cubic phases, formed by self-assembly processes of A-Na, have been observed. At room temperature and low humidity conditions (RH < 55%), the studied wedge-shaped molecule forms a columnar hexagonal mesophase (Col_{hd}), where the sulfonate groups are located on

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the column axis, giving rise to a well-defined ion-transporting channel.[32] The A-Na molecule presents an interesting example of a mesogen the structure of which can be arrested by photopolymerization [32-34]. The molecular structure of A-Na was inspired by the idea of Kato and colleagues of introducing polymerizable moieties into the chemical structure of the mesogen.[15] Photopolymerization was shown to produce mechanically stable materials suitable for membrane applications when the structure and orientation of the initial mesophase can be efficiently controlled.

Here, we demonstrate how nanoporous Anodic Aluminum Oxide templates (AAO) can be used to achieve homeotropic alignment of the Col_{hd} mesophase formed by the A-Na sulfonate molecule on large areas of thick membranes (~ 80 μm thick). As it was shown, the orientation of the 1D-confined Col_{hd} phase inside the porous structure of the AAO is transmitted to the film deposited on top of the membrane, forcing the supramolecular columns to orient perpendicularly to the plane of the membrane.

Results and Discussion

Initially, the influence of the surface energy and topography on the morphology of the A-Na columnar mesophase on thin films was evaluated. The obtained results are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. (a) 2D GIXS patterns of A-Na thin films spin-coated over Si (left) and ITO (right). The Miller indices of Col_{hd} phase are indicated. (b) 2D GIXS pattern of A-Na film prepared over PTFE-rubbed Si substrate. Reflection testifying the presence of PTFE is indicated in the meridian (left). Enlarged area showing peaks corresponding to the Col_{hd} phase is shown on the right. (c) 2D GIXS patterns of samples with different thickness. (d) Schematic view of the in plane alignment of hexagonal columnar phase. Self-assembly of A-Na results in tetramers that are in turn stacked on top of each other to form supramolecular cylinders.

Three different substrates were employed: bare Si wafers, ITO coated glass slides (substrate with high surface energy) and PTFE-rubbed Si substrates, which, besides the low surface energy value, were used previously to induce homeotropic alignment of columnar phases.[24] Films with different thickness (tens to hundreds of nm) were prepared by spin-coating or solution casting over Si substrates. The morphology of the films was studied by means of Grazing Incidence X-ray Scattering (GIXS), which has been proved as a powerful

technique for investigation of mesophases formed in thin films.[32-37] Fig. 1a shows the 2D X-ray patterns obtained from spin coated A-Na films over Si and ITO substrates. GIXS reveals the same highly oriented textures in both cases. The ratio between d-spacings was found to be 1:√3:2 which confirms the presence of a Col_{hd} phase. Miller indices of these reflections are indicated. The column diameter corresponding to the lattice parameter $a=39.2 \text{ \AA}$ remains constant for all the samples. Characteristic 6-spot pattern on 2D-diffractogram can be assigned to a planar alignment of the Col_{hd}, with the columnar axis lying parallel to the substrate, as schematically depicted in Fig. 1d. In the X-ray pattern corresponding to the film prepared over ITO, the refraction effects of the incidence beam due to the presence of ITO layer can be clearly observed in the meridian of the pattern.

In order to study the influence of the substrate topography thin films of A-Na were spin-coated over PTFE-rubbed substrates prepared as described in ref. [24]. In this case, the quality of the PTFE surface was confirmed by GIXS and Atomic Force microscopy (AFM) (see supporting info). Figure 1b-left shows a 2D pattern of the A-Na films spin coated over nanopatterned PTFE. The meridional peak located at wider angle corresponds to the d-spacing of 4.9 \AA . This reflection indicates that the PTFE rubbed film has a hexagonal phase with a unit cell parameter $a=5.7 \text{ \AA}$, in good agreement with the data reported in the literature [38]. The reflections corresponding to the A-Na Col_{hd} mesophase are located at smaller angles (Fig. 1b-right), showing the same d-spacings and angular distribution as the ones observed in previous samples.

Finally, the influence of film thickness and thermal treatments was also checked. Fig. 1c allows comparing the GIXS patterns corresponding to spin-coated and solution casted films, with different thicknesses. As can be observed, the in-plane orientation of the Col_{hd} phase is preserved on a thicker sample, even if the azimuthal broadening of the peaks indicates that the degree of orientation in this case is lower. Thermal treatments including annealing of the film about the isotropization point followed by slow cooling did not affect significantly the final morphology and the in-plane orientation of the columns (see Supporting Information).

According to the results obtained, the forces acting at the A-Na/air interface strongly favour the in-plane orientation of the mesophase over the homeotropic one: the in-plane orientation largely dominates, as was previously reported for different systems.[18,37,39]. In principle, this fact emphasizes the challenge of obtaining homeotropically aligned open films. nevertheless, it is possible to take advantage of this trend if a different approach is used.

Nanoporous materials, like Anodic Aluminum Oxide (AAO) membranes, have shown to be an effective substrate to induce orientation of liquid crystalline mesogens due to spatial confinement effects.[40-41] As pointed out by Steinhart et al., orientation due to confinement competes with orientation imposed by the surface interaction with the pore walls.[40] Due to the characteristics of our system, the "in-plane" orientation is expected to occur inside the pores. If so, on the one hand, we can overcome the mentioned problem of mixture of the two

orientations. On the other hand, it is reasonable to assume that the confinement imposed by the pore walls will induce orientation of the Col_{hd} supramolecular structure formed by A-Na in register with the columns lying parallel to the pore axis. Template wetting process was used to infiltrate AAO porous templates. Figure 2a shows a SEM image of the template.

Figure 2. (a) SEM image of the 25nm pore size AAO template used in this work. Inset shows GISAXS pattern obtained at $\alpha_i=0^\circ$. Reflections corresponding to the hexagonal packing of the pores are indicated. (b) Schematic view of the infiltration procedure of the AAO template. (c) Optical image of the cross section of the sample studied. Red pointed line indicates the scanning direction. Areas corresponding to the A-Na film, AAO membrane and air are indicated as 1 and 2 respectively.

Inset overlaid on the SEM image corresponds to the GISAXS pattern obtained at $\alpha_i=0^\circ$, with the X-ray beam parallel to the template plane. Several reflections corresponding to hexagonal arrangement of the pores in the template are indicated. A film of A-Na salt was blade coated by spreading a drop of the liquid crystal over the surface of the template. The sample was kept at $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, i.e. close to the isotropization temperature of the mesophase, under vacuum for 24 hours to favour complete filling of the membrane (Figure 2b).

Synchrotron X-ray microdiffraction was used for the structural characterization of the samples. The advantage of using small-sized beams to elucidate the structural changes due to the quasi-1D confinement realized inside the pores has been demonstrated.[38,42] An X-ray beam of 200 nm in diameter was used to scan along the cross section of the sample, with the beam parallel to the film surface (Fig. 2c). Diffraction patterns were collected at intervals of $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ allowing comparison of the structure and orientation of the mesophase in different regions

of the sample, which are located on the remnant film, as well as inside the AAO template (cf. positions 1 and 2 in Fig. 2c, respectively). Figure 3a shows the corresponding 2D X-ray patterns. Amplifications of the low angle region are shown on the right for each case.

Radial integration using the whole angular region allows to obtain the 1D-reduced curve shown in Fig. 3b, where the scattering intensity is represented as a function of the norm of the scattering vector s . X-ray diffractogram corresponding to the pattern obtained in region 1 displays five characteristic reflections at $s=0.029, 0.049, 0.057, 0.075$ and 0.085 \AA^{-1} (cf. Fig. 3b). The ratio of the corresponding d -spacings was found to be $1:\sqrt{3}:2:\sqrt{7}:3$ which allowed assigning them to 10, 11, 20, 21 and 30 reflections of a 2D Col_{hd} lattice with columnar diameter a of

41.5 \AA , in good agreement with the values previously reported for thin films.[24] At wider angles the presence of the characteristic halo due to stacking of the aliphatic chains is observed.[43] The structural parameters are the same inside the pores. The absorption of the sample generates the appearance of a sample image visible as a vertical shadow. The scattering intensity pertinent to the diffraction peaks is not homogeneously distributed along the diffraction circles, i.e. varies with the azimuthal angle. This reflects the existence of preferred orientation of the Col_{hd} mesophase along pore axis. In order to evaluate the orientation of the columnar phase, a detailed study of the azimuthal distribution of scattered intensity was accomplished. The azimuthal intensity of the 10 reflection was represented as a function of the beam position during the scan (Figure 4a).

Figure 4. (a) Azimuthal intensity of the 10 reflection of the Col_{hd} phase as a function of position of the incident X-ray beam in respect to the membrane surface. Interfaces AAO template/A-Na film and A-Na film/air are indicated by yellow and blue horizontal bars, respectively. (b) 2D X-ray pattern indicating the region of interest (between blue rings) for the azimuthal integration corresponding to the 10 reflection as well as the reference angles used in the study. (c) Schematic view of the orientation of the columnar mesophase inside and outside the porous structure. The favoured ionic transport direction is indicated by the blue arrow. (d)

Herman's orientation factor as a function of distance calculated for the A-Na film deposited over AAO template. The corresponding interfaces shown in (a) are indicated with vertical bars. Blue line is the fit of the experimental data with the exponential function.

The interfaces AAO template/A-Na film and A-Na film/air are indicated on the figure with yellow and blue horizontal bars, respectively. According to the scheme shown in Fig. 4b the meridional direction is located at azimuth angles of 90° and 270°. Although the scattered intensity coming from the infiltrated material is weaker than that generated by the remnant A-Na film, the existence of anisotropy can be clearly inferred from the azimuthal intensity distribution.

The Herman's orientation function (f_2) for uniaxially oriented systems defined as:

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{2}(3\langle \cos^2 \varphi \rangle - 1)$$

where φ is the angle between the azimuthal direction and reference axis. The f_2 function is commonly used to estimate the orientation of a sample from the analysis of wide or small-angle X-ray scattering data.[37,39] In this work, the Herman's orientation function was used to evaluate the columnar orientation of the mesophase. The s -range was adjusted for evaluation of the orientation of the 10 peak of the Col_{hd} phase. The directions of reference are indicated in Fig. 4b. For convenience, zero position for the calculation of f_2 was chosen at the meridian of the pattern ($\varphi=90^\circ$), since the scattered intensity reaches maximum in this region. Prior to calculation of the f_2 function, the scattering curves were normalized after subtraction of the background. According to the chosen reference system, the orientation function takes the value of 1 when the scattered intensity fully concentrates on the meridian and -0.5 when it concentrates on the equator. It is worth to mention that the scattering direction of the 10 reflection of the Col_{hd} structure is perpendicular to that of the columnar axis in the mesophase.

The measurements show that the columns are oriented parallel to the pore walls inside the AAO template, as it was expected. The unexpected fact is that the orientation of the columnar axis is preserved through the whole thickness of the remnant film, as schematically depicted in Fig. 4c. This means that the columns are oriented normal to the membrane surface. The orientation function f_2 decays with the increase of the distance from the interface with the AAO template; the corresponding characteristic decay distance evaluated from the exponential fit equals 35 μm (Fig. 4d). Nevertheless, the value of f_2 remains higher than ca. 0.4 at the A-Na film/air interface, which is about 70 μm far away from the first interface. This emphasizes the importance of the 1D confinement inside the pores for the orientation of the surface film.

The existence of homeotropic orientation was independently confirmed by using polarized optical microscopy. A film of A-Na prepared as previously described was deposited on a glass cover. A reference sample was prepared substituting the AAO template by a second glass cover. Figure 5a shows the POM images obtained before and after the infiltration procedure for

both systems. Initially, the same birefringence texture is observed (left images on each case). After the thermal treatment, the birefringence of the A-Na film sandwiched between glass covers seems to be improved. In the case of the sample prepared using the AAO template, the sample loses its birefringence and the corresponding POM image turns black when observed between crossed polarizers, which indicates the formation of a homeotropically aligned columnar mesophase.[15,21,24] The degree of orientation of the Col_{hd} for each case is schematically shown on the insets.

Under these conditions, is expected that unidirectional ionic transportation is favoured. In order to evaluate the effect of the orientation on the conductive properties of the material ion conductivity measurements were accomplished. Through-plane ion conductivity was measured at 25 °C by AC impedance spectroscopy at different relative humidity conditions (RH). Due to the high resistance of the AAO template, the opposite side to that in contact with the A-Na film was coated with gold to ensure electrical contact of the conductive paths formed through the porous with the ITO electrode. The reference sample was sandwiched between ITO coated glass slides. Schematic views of the cross-section of the setups used in each case are shown in Figure 5b.

Figure 5. (a) POM images of A-Na films prepared between cover glasses (top) or using AAO template (bottom); before (left) and after (right) thermal treatment for the infiltration of the porous template. (b) Schematic view of the setup used to test the conductivity of the different samples prepared directly between ITO electrodes (left) or using AAO templates (right). (c) Conductivity of samples prepared using different methods measured under dry conditions and at RH=33%. The value of conductivity extrapolated taking into account geometrical considerations is indicated with striped area.

Under dry conditions both samples show similar conductivities, in the range of $5.5 \times 10^{-5} \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ (cf. Fig. 5c). In absence of water no conductivity is observed. This behavior is similar to that observed for Nafion membranes, where presence of water is a requisite to reach high ion conductivity.[44-45] When RH increases up to 33%, a jump in the conductivity values is observed. While the reference sample reaches conductivity values of around $2.5 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, the A-Na film with ionic channels oriented perpendicular to its surface reaches 2.1×10^{-1}

$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, that is, almost one order of magnitude higher. The limited amount of conductive paths through the pores of the AAO template diminishes the effective contact area of the electrode with the membrane. According to geometrical considerations, only about 10-12% of the membrane surface contributes to the measured value of conductivity. In this case, the total resistance of the sample can be considered then as the sum of the resistances of two layers: the aligned A-Na film and the infiltrated AAO template. According to our calculations, the real conductivity of the uniaxially oriented membrane is on the order of $10 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$, that is, two orders of magnitude higher than the isotropic film value.

Conclusions

Orientation of an ion-channel forming columnar mesophase formed by self-assembly of a wedge-shaped sulfonate molecule was addressed for 1D-confinement within anodic aluminum oxide membranes. The director vector of the mesophase was found to be oriented parallel to the pore axis inside the AAO structure. The molecular arrangement induced by the spatial confinement within the pores is extended over several microns into the remnant film on the AAO surface. The homeotropic alignment of the channels favours 1D ion conduction through the film providing a dramatic increase of the out-of-plane conductivity compared to that observed for isotropic samples which opens perspectives for self-assembled ionomeric materials with improved performance.

Experimental Section

Sample preparation: Si substrates (ITME, Institute of Electronic Materials Technology Warszawa, Poland) were cleaned using piranha solution ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$, 3:1) prior to use on each case. Highly oriented PTFE-rubbed surface was obtained with a home-built device by sliding a PTFE rod at 330°C at a speed of $0.6 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. AAO templates (Whatman, nominal pore size: 25 nm diameter, 60 μm thick) and ITO substrates ($70\text{-}100 \Omega/\text{sq}$, Sigma-Aldrich) were cleaned by immersion in ultrasound bath with methanol for 30 minutes.

Thin films were prepared by spin-coating from A-Na solutions in CHCl_3 (20 mg ml^{-1}) over rotating substrates, applying a rotation speed of 2500 rpm during 45 s. In the case of solvent cast films, solution was deposited and slow solvent evaporation took place inside the lab hood.

Prior to conductivity measurements, the samples were annealed at 25°C inside sealed vials under RH=33% using saturated solution of MgCl_2 for 60 h, and then measured under the same conditions. The so called “dry” sample was dried and kept under vacuum.

Sample characterization: GIXS measurements were accomplished at BW4 beamline at the Hamburger Synchrotronstrahlungslabor (HASYLAB) at Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) (Hamburg, Germany) and X6B beamline at Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) (New York, EEUU). Wavelengths used were 1.38 and 0.68 Å, respectively.

Incidence angles (α_i) of 0° or 0.4° were chosen, depending on the sample. 2D X-ray patterns were recorded using CCD detectors (marCCD165 and PI-SCX-4300, Princeton Instruments). The modulus of the scattering vector s was calculated using several diffraction orders of silver behenate.

Microfocus XRD experiments in transmission geometry were carried out at the ID13 beamline at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) (Grenoble, France). The wavelength used was 0.81 Å. X-ray patterns were recorded by a two-dimensional CCD camera (FReLoN Kodak CCD). The sample-to-detector distance was calibrated by using a silver behenate standard.

Optical micrographs using polarized light were obtained by means of a LEITZ Laborlux 12 POL- S equipped with a digital camera DCM 310 with a C-mount.

Through-plane ion conductivity was measured at 25 °C by impedance spectroscopy using an Electrochemical Work-station IM6 (Zahner-Elektrik GmbH&Co. KG, Germany). The spectra were recorded with an amplitude of 1V in the frequency range from 100 to 10⁸ Hz. The conductivity values were obtained by fitting the impedance spectra with a model containing a serial connection of a parallel and a serial RC-circuits.

Author Contributions

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Conflicts of interest

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